

From squiggle to sequence:
Bioinformatics in the era of single-molecule biopolymer analysis

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Supplementary material

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FRETboard: semi-supervised classification of
FRET traces

Supplementary material

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3.1 Extended methods

3.1.1 Trace simulation

Simulated traces were generated by using a custom code written in Matlab (R2019b, The MathWorks, Inc.). A Markov chain Monte-Carlo (MCMC) procedure was used to generate hidden state paths according to a given transition matrix. The donor and acceptor fluorescence intensity traces were then generated from the hidden paths, using given emission distributions of single or mixed Gaussian per state. The widths of the Gaussian distributions were set to the square root of the mean to mimic the photon shot noise contribution. Additional random background noise was further added to simulate the dark count of the photo detector and the electronics shot noise. The traces were then downsampled to one tenth of the original length to simulate discrete measurement behaviour on a continuous biological process. For each dye labeling scheme, 300 single molecule traces were generated and used to test the performance of FRETboard. The length of each individual trace was randomly chosen between 12000 to 18000 data points before down-sampling in all except the 11-state case, for which 24000 to 36000 data points were used, to an exposure time of 1.0s. The simulation code is freely available upon request.

3.1.2 Extended experimental methods

Single-molecule setup

All experiments were performed on a custom-built microscope setup. An inverted microscope (IX73, Olympus) with prism-based total internal reflection is used. In combination with a 532 nm DPSS laser (Compass 215M/50mW, Coherent). A 60x water immersion objective (UPLSAPO60XW, Olympus) was used for the collection of photons from the Cy3 and Cy5 dyes on the surface, after which a 532 nm long pass filter (LDP01-532RU-25, Semrock) blocks the excitation light. A dichroic mirror (635 dcr, Chroma) separates the fluorescence signal which is then projected onto an EM-CCD camera (iXon Ultra, DU-897U-CS0-#BV, Andor Technology). A series of EM-CCD images was recorded at an exposure time of 0.1s, using a custom-made program in Visual C++ (Microsoft). Time traces were extracted from the EM-CCD images using IDL (ITT Visual Information Solution).

Single-molecule data acquisition

To avoid non-specific binding of DNA to the surface, quartz slides were PEGylated as previously described [1]. Briefly, acidic piranha etched quartz slides (Finkenbeiner) were passivated twice with polyethylene glycol (PEG). The first round PEGylation was performed with mPEG-SVA (Laysan) and PEG-biotin (Laysan), followed by a second round of PEGylation with MS(PEG)4 (ThermoFisher). After assembly of a microfluidic chamber, the slides were incubated with 20 μ L streptavidin (0.1 mg/mL, ThermoFisher) for 2 minutes. Excess streptavidin was removed with 100 μ L T50.

Next, for single-molecule experiments we immobilized 50 μL of 100 pM Cy5 (or Cy3) labelled target DNA for 2 minutes, unbound DNA was washed with 100 μL T50, followed by 100 μL of buffer A (50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0, 500 mM NaCl). Next, we injected 50 μL of 5 nM imager strands in imaging buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0, 500 mM NaCl, 0.8% glucose, 0.5 mg/mL glucose oxidase (Sigma), 85 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ catalase (Merck) and 1 mM Trolox (Sigma). The single-molecule FRET experiments were performed at room temperature (23 ± 2 °C).

Manual classification

For each experiment, 100 traces were manually classified using a custom python script, found at https://git.wageningenur.nl/lanno001/fretboard_data/-/blob/master/scripts/tracer_viewer.py. All manual classifications were done in one sitting and by the same person (C.L.) to avoid different user biases between data sets.

3.1.3 Semi-supervised model fitting

Fitting a vanilla Hidden Markov Model

If manually labeled traces are available, the set of all parameters (θ) for a Hidden Markov model (HMM) can be fitted in a supervised fashion; emission probabilities may be estimated by fitting a probability distribution to features for each state, while transition probabilities are deduced from the state sequence. To fit Gaussian distributions to our features for each state i given labeled traces $X_n, n = 1 \dots N$, of variable length T_n , we calculate the mean μ_i^* and standard deviation σ_i^{2*} over all measurements x_{nt} of which the corresponding label L_{nt} equals i :

$$\mu_i^* = \frac{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} x_{nt} \delta_{L_{nt}i}}{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i}} \quad \sigma_i^{2*} = \frac{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} (\mu_i - x_{nt})^2 \delta_{L_{nt}i}}{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i}} \quad (3.1)$$

Here $\delta_{L_{nt}i}$ equals 1 if $L_{nt} = i$, and 0 if $L_{nt} \neq i$. The transition probabilities are estimated as the ratio of transitions between two states over the number of occurrences of the departure state:

$$a_{ij}^* = \frac{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n-1} \delta_{L_{nt}i} \delta_{L_{n(t+1)j}}}{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n-1} \delta_{L_{nt}i}} \quad (3.2)$$

Here a_{ij}^* denotes the estimated entry (i, j) in the HMM's transition matrix, i.e. the probability of transitioning from state i to j . Finally, the starting probabilities per state can be derived by taking the fraction of labeled traces that start with a given state:

$$\pi_i = \frac{\sum_n^N \delta_{L_{n1}i}}{|N|} \quad (3.3)$$

Manually labeling sufficient data to capture all distinctive patterns in traces is laborious, thus HMMs are often fitted unsupervised, using an implementation of expectation maximization known as Baum-Welch training. By iteratively alternating between re-estimating model parameters and producing the most likely labeling given model parameters and data, an HMM can be fitted without prior knowledge of either the correct sequence labeling or model parameters. In that case the contribution of each sample to the parameters for the emission distribution of a class i and a given transition a_{ij} is weighted by the probabilities of assignment to that class $\gamma_i(n, t)$ and the transition occurring $\xi_{ij}(n, t)$ respectively, given the current model parameters:

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_i(n, t) &= \frac{P(L_{nt} = i, X_n | \theta)}{P(X_n | \theta)} \\ \xi_{ij}(n, t) &= \frac{P(L_{nt} = i, L_{n(t+1)} = j, X_n | \theta)}{P(X_n | \theta)}\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

Fitting using the supervised procedure effectively sets the probabilities for observed states and transitions to 1 and all others to 0 by means of $\delta_{L_{nt}i}$ in equations 3.1 and 3.2.

As noted in the main text, Baum-Welch training requires initial values for transition and emission parameters, and given its greedy nature may not converge to a satisfactory optimum. If semi-supervised learning is employed, initial emission distributions and transition probabilities can be estimated using a manually labeled subset of all traces and equations 3.1 and 3.2. Then training can proceed using the Baum-Welch procedure on labeled and unlabeled data, where the labels of classified examples need not be re-estimated (equations 3.5). In this way, the training procedure may be steered towards finding a model that reproduces the classification in the labeled traces, while still being able to fit patterns that were only present in the unlabeled traces.

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_i^* &= \lambda \cdot \frac{\overbrace{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} x_{nt} \delta_{L_{nt}i}}^{\text{supervised}}}{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i}} + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \frac{\overbrace{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m} \gamma_i(t) x_{mt}}^{\text{unsupervised}}}{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m} \gamma_i(t)} \\ \sigma_i^{2*} &= \lambda \cdot \frac{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i} (x_{nt}^* - \mu_i)^2}{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i}} + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \frac{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m} \gamma_i(t) (x_{mt}^* - \mu_i)^2}{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m} \gamma_i(t)} \\ a_{ij}^* &= \lambda \cdot \frac{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n-1} \delta_{L_{nt}i} \delta_{L_{n(t+1)}j}}{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n-1} \delta_{L_{nt}i}} + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \frac{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m-1} \xi_{ij}(t)}{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m-1} \gamma_i(t)}\end{aligned}\tag{3.5}$$

Here N denotes the number of manually labeled traces and M denotes the number of unlabeled traces. We may choose to increase the additional tuning parameter λ if we find that the model does not reproduce our labeled sequences sufficiently well anymore. Note that for $\lambda = 1$ the procedure resorts to fully supervised fitting, which requires no Baum-Welch training. By default, λ is set to 0.5, meaning that all supervised and unsupervised traces carry the same weight.

Fitting a GMM-HMM

The GMM-HMM structure differs from the vanilla HMM implementation in two respects: (1) each state is modeled using a Gaussian mixture model (GMM) and (2) between each pair of states an additional state - referred to as "edge state" - is added to model the transition between states explicitly. The fitting procedure for a GMM-HMM is largely the same as that for vanilla HMMs described above. As GMMs have taken the place of the single Gaussian distributions, the maximization step of the HMM now should include mean and standard deviation estimation for G Gaussians and their weights ($\mu_{ig}, \sigma_{ig}, \alpha_{ig} \forall g \in G$) for each state i . To estimate these parameters another EM procedure is ran for each state, for each HMM maximization step. First, membership weights for each measurement are calculated using current GMM parameters.

$$w(i, g, x) = \frac{P(x|\mu_{ig}, \sigma_{ig})\alpha_{ig}}{\sum_h P(x|\mu_{ih}, \sigma_{ih})\alpha_{ih}} \quad (3.6)$$

Then membership weights are used to re-estimate GMM parameters.

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{ig}^* &= \lambda \cdot \frac{\overbrace{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i} w(i, g, x_{nt})}^{\text{supervised}}}{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i}} + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \frac{\overbrace{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m} \gamma_i(t) w(i, g, x_{mt})}^{\text{unsupervised}}}{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m} \gamma_i(t)} \\ \mu_{ig}^* &= \lambda \cdot \frac{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i} w(i, g, x_{nt}) x_{nt}}{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i}} + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \frac{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m} \gamma_i(t) w(i, g, x_{mt}) x_{mt}}{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m} \gamma_i(t)} \\ \sigma_{ig}^{2*} &= \lambda \cdot \frac{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i} (x_{nt} - \mu_{ig}^*)^2 w(i, g, x_{nt})}{\sum_n^N \sum_t^{T_n} \delta_{L_{nt}i}} + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \frac{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m} \gamma_i(t) (x_{mt} - \mu_{ig}^*)^2 w(i, g, x_{mt})}{\sum_m^M \sum_t^{T_m} \gamma_i(t)} \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

Iterations continue until the log-likelihood of the data increases no more than 0.1 or after a maximum of 10^8 iterations, whichever occurs first. This is the standard behavior for GMM optimization in pomegranate, the package used to implement GMMs. The added edge states are implemented by fixing the transition probabilities

between states, between all pairs of edge states and edge state self-transitions to 0, thus forcing transitions between states to take place through the edge states. In all other respects, the training procedure remains unchanged.

3.1.4 Trace correction using FRETboard

As FRET efficiency is influenced by background irradiance, detector efficiency differences, cross-talk between acceptor and donor channels, direct excitation of acceptor dyes and background emission, it is advisable to apply some form of filtering to raw traces prior to classifier training.

FRETboard offers an automated per-trace background subtraction method for donor and acceptor channels separately. Using the DBSCAN clustering algorithm [2] the lowest intensity level in the channel is detected and subtracted. Prerequisite for proper functioning of this adaptive filter is that the trace does contain a stretch of background-level intensity irradiance. Stringency of this filter is controlled by the tunable ϵ parameter, which is defined as the maximum distance between a cluster's core point and distant points of the same cluster. A preset value of $\epsilon = 15$ was found to work in all data presented here.

If alternating laser excitation (ALEX) data is available, FRETboard can automatically apply cross-talk, direct excitation and detector efficiency corrections as described in [3], by marking certain states as *D*(onor)-only and *A*(cceptor)-only. FRETboard will subsequently perform the necessary calculations to estimate and apply correction coefficients.

3.1.5 Trace analysis using different tools

To compare our method to other tools, we analyzed our *in vitro* data using three other tools and compared their estimates of FRET distribution parameters and transition rates to those based on manual analysis and the FRETboard results. Below we describe the workflows we followed for each tool.

ebFRET

ebFRET employs a Bayesian approach to deduce parameters for an HMM from a data set of traces, by fitting on individual traces and estimating parameter distributions. Here we used the GUI version of ebFRET (v1.1.1). For the donor-immobilized dataset we detected bleaching using the built-in bleaching removal option. For the main analysis we fixed the number of states at the correct value. As this tool does not generate confidence intervals for transition rates, an adapted version was written which generates these by bootstrapping the data (adapted version available at <https://github.com/cvdelannoy/ebfret-gui>).

MASH-FRET

The MASH-FRET software suite (v1.3.1, commit 48221723) offers its users an array of software tools to segment traces, after which histogram analysis and transition analysis can be applied. For the donor-immobilized dataset, bleaching was detected using the built-in bleaching removal option. We used the provided STaSI implementation to segment traces as we found the best results for this tool upon visual inspection of segmentations. This was followed by transition analysis, in which the built-in BOBA-FRET implementation was used to generate confidence intervals. For both segmentation and transition analysis, we provided the tool with the correct number of states. On the donor-only dataset analysis was performed on the E_{PR} signal. For the other data sets the E_{PR} at ground state was not meaningful due to the absence of a donor dye, and indeed did not allow for effective state detection. We therefore segmented traces using the acceptor signal and used a custom script to derive segmented E_{PR} values instead.

DeepFRET

DeepFRET utilizes a pre-trained neural network to separate stretches of traces containing containing FRET events from noisy and bleached stretches, after which a fully-connected HMM is used to classify traces and extract the HMM parameter values. Only the analysis of donor-immobilized traces is shown, as only these traces were of a structure recognized by DeepFRET (i.e. with presence of the donor in ground-FRET state). For the other datasets, the donor-less ground state was erroneously interpreted as bleaching, rendering effective analysis impossible. Furthermore DeepFRET does not allow the user to define the number of states, thus this could not be enforced as was done for the other tools.

Comparison results

For donor-immobilized two-state traces, we find that ebFRET, MASH-FRET and FRETboard return FRET efficiency distributions and transition rates similar to those found in manual analysis (Figure 3.S9A,E). DeepFRET erroneously detected five states for this data, with means of 0.36, 0.16, 1.0, 0.15 and 0.74. Upon visual inspection of the traces, we found that at least some additional states were represented in bleaching events.

For the remaining three experiments the acceptor dye was immobilized rather than the donor dye. As the donor dye is absent at ground FRET signal in these traces, the FRET signal heavily fluctuates, rendering it meaningless. As ebFRET only analyses FRET signal and not the individual donor and acceptor emission channels, we found that the ground-state FRET signal was not properly recognized, disallowing reliable analysis. Evidently ebFRET was not designed for this type of data, thus we omitted it from comparison for these experiments. Similarly, DeepFRET's neural network was unfit to analyse these traces as it erroneously interpreted the donor-less ground state as bleaching or scrambled signal. The HMM classification functionality of DeepFRET

was still functional, but was also unable to produce convincing results. We conclude that DeepFRET was also not designed for this usage, and thus omit it from further comparison.

MASH-FRET produced reasonable estimates for both FRET distribution parameters and transition rates (Figure 3.S9B-D, F-H). However FRET distribution mean was consistently underestimated and variance was overestimated. In the kinetic fingerprinting experiment (D,H), a higher transition rate was detected for the degenerate second state, however the predicted rate was lower than the value found through manual analysis. We conclude that of the evaluated tools, only FRETboard has shown the flexibility to effectively adapt to data produced by different labeling schemes.

3.2 Supplementary figures

Figure 3.S1: Controls in the graphical user interface are divided in three steps: **[1]** loading data and model structure, **[2]** iteratively teaching the chosen model structure to recognize events as the user sees fit and **[3]** saving a report with statistics and publication-ready figures, the raw classified data for further processing and the model for future use on similar datasets.

Figure 3.S2: Example sections of simulated FRET traces and ground truth classification for four scenarios: (A) one FRET state, (B) one FRET state with immobilized acceptor and mobile donor (C) two FRET states and (D) ten FRET states. White background denotes the ground state while different shades of gray denote different states.

Figure 3.S3: Distribution of log-probabilities of traces given hidden Markov model (HMM) parameters θ , normalized over trace duration T_n . Of 300 traces shown, 150 contained two states (Supplementary figure 3.S2A) and 150 contained three (Figure 3.S2B), however the HMM was parameterized and trained as a vanilla 2-state model. These data show that 3-state traces show substantially lower normalized log-probabilities. As FRETboard selects traces with the lowest normalized log-probability for manual supervision, the user is more likely to be shown the 3-state traces, allowing them to reconsider the model parameterization.

Figure 3.S4: Performance measures of FRETboard at increasing numbers of supervised examples, on a simulated 3-state data set, with a signal-to-noise ratio of 25.5. **A-C**: proximity ratio distributions after 0, 1 and 5 rounds of semi-supervised training respectively. Note that at 0 rounds, only an unsupervised training round has taken place. **D**, **E**: proximity ratio and transition rate estimates (resp.) plotted against number of semi-supervised training rounds. Whiskers denote bootstrapped 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 3.S5: Kernel density estimates of E_{PR} distributions per state (A) and transition rates (B) as estimated by a semi-supervised vanilla hidden Markov model on a simulated dataset containing eleven separable states. Ground truth parameters are displayed as dotted lines in each figure. In B, circle surface indicates transition rate. In comparison, analysis using the GMM-HMM model structure (Figure 3D,H) returned parameter estimates closer to ground truth values for both transition rates and E_{PR} distributions per state.

Figure 3.S6: Performance measures of FRETboard on six simulated 3-state data sets, in which the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is varied. **A**: representative examples of the six included SNR levels. **B**, **C**: proximity ratio (E_{PR}) estimates per state and transition rate estimates (respectively). Whiskers denote bootstrapped 95% confidence intervals. **C**: transition rate estimates. **D**: Accuracy of manual classifications by the user, which are provided to FRETboard as supervised examples (dotted line) and accuracy of classification by the trained GMM-HMM model (solid line).

Figure 3.S7: Used labeling schemes (**A-D**), kernel density estimates of proximity ratio (E_{PR}) distributions per state (**E-H**) and estimated transition rates (**I-L**) for four different labeling schemes on which our semi-supervised HMM fitting method with vanilla structure was evaluated. From left to right, these labeling schemes were producing single-type FRET events using an immobilized donor (**A**) or an immobilized acceptor (**B**), two types of events producing high- and mid-FRET events (**C**) and two types of kinetically different events (**D**). In E-L, dotted lines represent ground truth values based on manual labeling and in I-L solid lines denote bootstrapped 95% CIs. In comparison, analysis using the GMM-HMM model structure (Figure 4I-P) returned parameter estimates closer to ground truth values for both transition rates and E_{PR} distributions per state.

Figure 3.S8: Count histograms, subdivided per manually selected (dotted line) and FRETboard-classified (solid line) state, for four *in vitro* data sets generated using four different labeling schemes. These labeling schemes produced (A) a single type of FRET events using an immobilized donor (A), a single type with an immobilized acceptor (B), high- and mid-FRET events (C) and long and short events with the same FRET distribution (D). Non-FRET state (1) is not shown for acceptor-immobilized data (B,C,D) as the absence of the donor dye renders FRET value meaningless.

Figure 3.S9: Comparison of predicted FRET efficiency distributions (**A-D**) and transition rates (**E-H**) for FRETboard and two other tools on experimental data, generated with four different labeling schemes. From left to right, these labeling schemes were producing single-type FRET events using an immobilized donor (**A,E**) and an immobilized acceptor (**B,F**), two types of events producing high- and mid-FRET events (**C,G**) and two types of kinetically different events (**D,H**). ebFRET results for experiments in which acceptor dyes were immobilized, as it was found to be incompatible with the resulting data structure. If events only differed kinetically, MASH-FRET was used to estimate a single FRET distribution for both and fit a double exponential to retrieve the second pair of transition rates, hence state 2 and 3 measurements in **D** are pooled as state 2 for MASH-FRET.

PoreTally: run and publish *de novo* Nanopore assembler benchmarks

Supplementary material

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4.1 The collective benchmark

poreTally was conceived to facilitate standardization of *de novo* nanopore assembly pipeline benchmarks and fast publication on the user's personal Github/Gitlab page. Although this method of publication allows for fast and independent dissemination of benchmark results, it may result in a fragmented view of overall assembly pipeline performance.

Figure 4.S1: Schematic representation of the poreTally collective benchmark submission process. If the user consents to submitting benchmark results, an empty repository will be forked to their account (1) after which the benchmark results are pushed to the fork (2) and a pull request is submitted (3). Periodically, we will accept made pull requests, summarize the results and publish the aggregated report in another repository (4).

Therefore we also included the option to submit results to a collective benchmark effort. Benchmarks submitted to this effort will be summarized and published online, thus giving a more unified indication of *de novo* assembly pipeline performance.

If a user chooses to support the collective benchmark, a dedicated Github repository will automatically be cloned to their account, after which results are pushed to that repository and a pull request is submitted (Figure 4.S1). The same data that would appear on a regular poreTally repository publication is submitted to the collective benchmark, thus no actual read or assembly sequences are shared. The submission process through Github allows for scalable and transparent data collection. Through the Github account used to submit a benchmark, its source can be traced back to the user, thus allowing us to duly credit submitters for their contribution and providing credibility to the collective benchmark.

Periodically we will accept pull requests and present a summary of submitted benchmarks in a separate repository: github.com/cvdelannoy/poreTallyCommunity. Given sufficient and sufficiently diverse submissions, we may eventually be able to better characterize factors that influence assembler performance for often-used pipelines, such as sequencing hardware, read set quality and species. As nanopore sequencers — and the MinION in particular — uniquely allow any individual researcher to complete the

genome sequencing process for any species from DNA sample to assembly, we envision that the collective benchmark will serve both the growing group of novel users and veterans alike when selecting the appropriate assembly pipeline for their data set and biological source.

BaseLess: lightweight detection of sequences in
raw MinION data

Supplementary material

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Figure 5.S1: BaseLess neural network structure for the recognition of different k -mers. A network for three k -mers is shown, although the structure can be expanded to an arbitrary number of k -mers. Starting from a squiggle segment, two 1D-convolution layers, a maxpool layer and dense layer are applied consecutively. A threshold on posterior probability is applied to produce a boolean indicating presence or absence of the target k -mer, after which results are concatenated. In abundance mode concatenated results are summed over all batches (not shown), while in read detection mode an additional rule is added to return a single boolean indicating whether the read contains a predefined minimum fraction of all target k -mers.

Table 5.S1: The 21 bacterial strains and associated GenBank assembly accessions used in the validation of the read detection mode of baseLess.

Species	GenBank Accession
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> , strain ATCC 17978	GCA_013372085.1
<i>Actinomyces odontolyticus</i> , strain ATCC 17982	GCA_000154225.1
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> , strain ATCC 10987	GCA_000008005.1
<i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i> , strain ATCC 8482	GCA_000012825.1
<i>Clostridium beijerinckii</i> , strain NCIMB 8052	GCA_000016965.1
<i>Deinococcus radiodurans</i> , strain R1 (smooth)	GCA_000008565.1
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> , strain OG1RF	GCA_004006275.1
<i>Escherichia coli</i> , strain K-12 MG1655	GCA_000005845.2
<i>Helicobacter pylori</i> , strain 26695	GCA_000008525.1
<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i> , strain ATCC 33323	GCA_000014425.1
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> , strain EGDe	GCA_000196035.1
<i>Neisseria meningitides</i> , strain MC58	GCA_000008805.1
<i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i> , strain ATCC 33277	GCA_000010505.1
<i>Propionibacterium acnes</i> , strain KPA171202	GCA_000008345.1
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> , strain PAO1-LAC	GCA_000006765.1
<i>Rhodobacter sphaeroides</i> , strain ATH 2.4.1	GCA_000012905.2
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , strain USA300_TCH1516	GCA_000017085.1
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> , strain ATCC 12228	GCA_000007645.1
<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i> , strain 2603 V/R	GCA_000007265.1
<i>Streptococcus mutans</i> , strain UA159	GCA_000007465.2
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i> , strain TIGR4	GCA_000006885.1

Evaluation of FRET X for single-molecule
protein fingerprinting

Supplementary material

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6.1 Supplementary figures

Figure 6.S1: pseudo-atoms on a cubic lattice (**A**) and a body-centered cubic lattice (**B**). Shown are one main pseudo-atom (red) and its direct neighbors (green). For the main pseudo-atom, all possible adjacent pseudo-atoms (green) are depicted. Figures were generated in Blender 2.93.0.

Figure 6.S2: Single-molecule binding kinetics of FRET X imager strands. (A) Dwell-time histogram for the FRET X donor imager strand (Supplementary Table 6.S2) fitted with a maximum likelihood estimation for a single exponential distribution (black line). Average \pm standard deviation of four different estimations gives: 2.1 ± 0.1 s. The number of data points for this distribution: $n = 4687$ and peptide used was K1C40. (B) Dwell-time histogram for the FRET X acceptor imager strand (Supplementary table 6.S2) fitted with a maximum likelihood estimation for a single exponential distribution (black line). Average \pm standard deviation of four different estimations gives: 1.9 ± 0.1 s. The number of data points for this distribution: $n = 9477$ and peptide used was K1C40.

Figure 6.S3: representative kymographs of individual peptides. (A-D) Representative single-molecule FRET kymographs for each of the four peptides. The downward FRET (E) trend remains at the single-molecule level and the distribution of each individual molecule can be fitted with high precision (s.d. ≤ 0.03 for each distribution). The ensemble of many identical single molecules results in the FRET fingerprint (Figure 6.3.2B).

Figure 6.S4: Histograms of simulated FRET events for a single molecule each of three Bcl spliceoforms. Cysteine and lysine-derived values are colored orange and purple respectively. The corresponding FRET X fingerprints, for which FRET values are averaged per tagged residue, are shown in Figure 6.3.

A

B

Figure 6.S5: Simulated FRET X fingerprints for spliceforms of BCL and PTGS1. **(A)** FRET X fingerprints for ten simulated molecules, one per horizontal line, of three BCL-X spliceforms: BCL-XL, BCL-XS and BCL-XB. Cysteine and lysine-derived values are colored orange and purple respectively. **(B)** FRET X fingerprints for ten simulated molecules of six PTGS1 spliceforms.

Figure 6.S6: SVM classifier accuracy on simulated fingerprints for 313 proteins at different resolutions. Average classifier accuracy versus the number of tagged residues in structures, aggregated in five groups with similar numbers of tags, at different resolutions. Data are shown for **(A)** optimal labeling quality (i.e. 100% efficiency, 100% specificity) and **(B)** suboptimal labeling quality (see Table 6.S3 for efficiency and specificity), for three combinations of tagged residues (C, C + K, and C + K + R). Whiskers denote two standard deviations.

Figure 6.S7: Schematic of FRET X fingerprinting simulation and classification pipeline used in this work. **(A)** Simulation starts from a fully atomistic structure, **(B)** which is first converted into a lattice model. In the lattice model all residues are reduced to their C_{α} positions. **(C)** Residues to which docking strands must be attached are marked, after which the structure is randomly mutated using a Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) process, until docking strands no longer experience steric hindrance from the rest of the structure. **(D)** The MCMC process then continues while snapshots are taken at regular intervals. Donor-acceptor dye distance for each dye pair is averaged over all snapshots and translated into a FRET efficiency. Combined, the FRET efficiencies form the final fingerprint for this molecule. **(E)** A support vector machine (SVM) is trained on a set of fingerprints with known identities, after which it can be used to classify unseen fingerprints.

Figure 6.S8: L-plectasin structure (3E7U) in four steps of the fingerprinting pipeline. **(A)** Fully atomistic structure as recorded in the RCSB protein database (PDB). Six cysteine residues (yellow) form the three disulfide bridges that connect the N-terminal alpha helix and C-terminal beta sheet. **(B)** The structure after translation to a lattice model. Disulfide bridges are marked as dotted lines. **(C)** Cysteines are targeted for tagging. Upon attachment of tags, cysteines lose their ability to interact with residues, thus cysteine bonds are lost. **(D)** After energy minimization, structure has largely been lost. Figures generated in pymol v2.3.0.

Figure 6.S9: The three structural modifications applied during energy minimization of lattice models. **(A)** A branch rotation rotates all pseudo-atoms before or after a chosen pseudo-atom, **(B)** a corner flip changes the position of a single pseudo-atom to another vertex connected to the neighboring pseudo-atoms and **(C)** a crankshaft move does the same for two neighboring pseudo-atoms simultaneously. Figures generated in pymol v2.3.0.

Figure 6.S10: Illustration of the tag repulsion implementation of the lattice model. If the distance between two tagged pseudo-atoms is found to be less than 20\AA , both the angle and the dihedral angle should be larger than 70° to obtain a valid tag position. Figure was generated in Blender 2.93.0.

Figure 6.S11: Lattice space occupied by a DNA-tag. Shown are a (A) side and (B) bottom view of an on-lattice backbone of the DNA-tag (purple), and the space it is assumed to occupy to account for the additional bulkiness of DNA nucleotides, when compared to amino acids. In this example, a single pseudo-atom from a different part of the structure (red) is incurring steric hindrance. Figure was generated in Blender 2.93.0.

6.2 Supplementary tables

Peptide	Sequence (N to C)	Modification	Supplier
K1C10	KAGERDNFACHMALVPVAAN DENYALAAAANDENYALAAA	Biotin-Ahx N-terminus	Biomatik (CAN)
K1C20	KAGERDNFAPHMALVPVAAC DENYALAAAANDENYALAAA	Biotin-Ahx N-terminus	Biomatik (CAN)
K1C30	KAGERDNFAPHMALVPVAAN DENYALAAACNDENYALAAA	Biotin-Ahx N-terminus	Biomatik (CAN)
K1C40	KAGERDNFAPHMALVPVAAN DENYALAAAANDENYALAAC	Biotin-Ahx N-terminus	Biomatik (CAN)

Table 6.S1: Single-molecule peptide constructs.

DNA strand	Sequence (5' - 3')	Modification	Supplier
Donor imager strand	AGATGTAT	3' Cy3	Ella Biotech (GmbH)
Acceptor imager strand	AATGAAGA	3' Cy5	Ella Biotech (GmbH)
Donor docking strand	TATACATCTAT	5' Maleimide	Biomers.net (GmbH)
Acceptor docking Strand	TTCTTCATTACT	5' Azidobenzoate	Biomers.net (GmbH)

Table 6.S2: Single-molecule DNA constructs.

Chemistry	Target	P(target labeling)	Off-target residue	P(Off-target labeling)	Ref.
Maleimide thiol reaction	C	90%	K	1%	[4]
NHS ester-mediated derivatization	K	90%	S,Y,T	1%	[5]
Arginine derivatization	R	90%	Any	0.5%	[6]

Table 6.S3: Labeling probabilities under suboptimal conditions.

Chop-n-Drop: *In silico* assessment of a novel single-molecule protein fingerprinting method employing fragmentation and nanopore detection

Supplementary material

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7.1 Supplementary figures

Figure 7.S1: **Excluded current of two peptides with a difference in mass of 4 Da, related to STAR methods.** Top panels show excluded current (I_{ex}) set against the dwell time of events observed, bottom panels show the excluded current histogram of the top panel. Data is shown for (A) [Met5]-Enkephalin (YGGFM), (B) [d-Ala2][d-Leu5]-Enkephalin (YdAGFdL) and (C) an equimolar mixture of the two peptides, with fitted Gaussians denoting the peak for each peptide.

Figure 7.S2: **Diagram of the dynamic programming algorithm used to align database and query chop-n-drop fingerprints, related to STAR methods.** (A) Numbers on the axes of the matrix denote fragment weights in Da. Weights involved in the displayed alignment step are black. The cells in the comparison matrix are filled row-wise starting from the top-left, by entering the alignment distance up to cell (i, j) in (i, j) . (B) To fill square (i, j) , two fragments of one fingerprint may be aligned to one fragment in the other, or single fragments may be aligned. A gap may also be introduced at a resolution-dependent penalty (not shown). (C) The option minimizing the summed distances of aligned fragments (Δ 's) up to (i, j) is chosen – in this case, two fragments of the database fingerprint are aligned to a single fragment of the target fingerprint. (D) The process is continued until the bottom right cell is filled. The value in this cell (S) is the alignment distance for this pair of fingerprints.

Figure 7.S3: **Representative examples of alignments between chop-n-drop query fingerprints and the best-matching database fingerprints, related to Figure 2.** Dotted lines denote aligned fragments. Fragments for which a gap was introduced are greyed-out. **(A)** Four correct alignments. **(B)** Two incorrect alignments (red) and corresponding correct alignments (green).

Figure 7.S4: **Distribution of sequence identities between misclassified proteins and the proteins for which they were mistaken based on their chop-n-drop fingerprint, related to Figure 2.** Random alignments are expected to generate a sequence identity of thirty percent on average.

Figure 7.S5: **Simulated fingerprint identification accuracy assuming charge-dependent fragment capture, related to Figures 2 and 3.** Cumulative histograms of correct and incorrect classifications of simulated chop-n-drop protein fingerprints for all human proteome constituents, accounting for fragment charge, related to Figures 2 and 3. Here it is assumed that fragments with a charge lower than -1 at $\text{pH}=4$ cannot pass the pore. Results are shown for (A) low-noise parameter settings (resolution $r = 5\text{Da}$, capture rate $C = 0.99$, proteasome efficiency $e_p = 0.99$) and (B) high-noise parameter settings ($r = 10\text{Da}$, $C = 0.99$, $e_p = 0.99$). Numbers are shown distributed over sequence length (bars), and relative to the total number of proteins (pie chart).

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